

DIGITAL COMPETENCE CENTRE

TU DELFT DCC

WHO WE ARE

The DCC is an on-campus initiative to coordinate and deliver data management and software engineering support required for 21st-century research. We help researchers at all levels develop competencies needed to conduct FAIR research by providing hands-on support with implementing data management workflows and developing research software. The DCC is an initiative of the Open Science Program at TU Delft.

OUR MISSION

Researchers at TU Delft regularly produce software and large datasets. Making these research outputs easier to find and reuse benefits the broader research community; efficient data storage and management, and FAIR software practices helps researchers to extend the value of their outputs beyond personal use.

WHY CARE ABOUT FAIR RESEARCH?

Make your research outputs **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.**

Adopting the FAIR principles into your research project will increase the relevance and value of your research outputs, from scientific publications to data and source code.

Science relies on the opportunity to understand and build upon work done by others. **When research outputs are not findable, code is not readable, or data published in papers is not easy to access; researchers struggle to make progress.**

In response, research funding bodies and open access journals are increasingly asking researchers to make their research outputs FAIR.

More than an ideal, the FAIR principles are a set of practices that can streamline the scientific process to enhance the value of research outputs.

OPEN SCIENCE

At TU Delft, through the Open Science Programme, our university is committed to making open research and open education a standard part of scientific practice, and the DCC is part of that commitment.

DCC@TUDELFT.NL

“It is our ambition to be the frontrunner in this area. Our aim is that Open Science becomes the default setting for research and education at TU Delft.”

Prof. dr. Rob Mudde
Vice-Rector Magnificus

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THE DCC SUPPORT TEAM

Our team provides researchers with IT skills, knowledge of best practices and toolkits required for implementing the FAIR principles into any research project.

We also accept assignments to work closely with research teams at TU Delft for a short period of up to six months. This type of support is aimed at research projects which develop scientific software as one of their outcomes, and/or require expert advice to design and implement data management workflows that make research outputs reusable and interoperable.

The DCC Support Team consists of data managers and research software engineers (RSE) based in the TU Delft Library and ICT/Innovation department. The team's purpose is to help researchers to gain knowledge and skills in applying the FAIR principles to their research activities and reach their software development goals.

Amir Fard
Data Manager

Ashley Cryan
Data Manager

Joé Urrua Llamusa
RSE

Manuel Garcia
RSE

Maurits Kok
RSE

Niket Agrawal
RSE

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HOW CAN WE HELP?

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Any researcher at TU Delft, including postdoctoral researchers and PhDs, can request support from our team of Data Managers and Research Software Engineers.

QUESTIONS ABOUT DATA MANAGEMENT & SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

If you have questions about data management workflows, best practices in software engineering, FAIR software or want to know more about the DCC; send your questions to our email address: dcc@tudelft.nl

Our team will reply to you directly or find the right person that can give you an answer.

PROJECT SUPPORT

Apply for extended support for your research projects (up to 340 hours during a period of six months). We can come 'onboard' and work with you!

In our website, you find information about the upcoming calls and deadlines.

GET IN TOUCH

 DCC Community Team

 <https://dcc.tudelft.nl>

DCC@TUDELFT.NL

SUPPORT AND SERVICES

TU DELFT DCC

FAIR DATA

- Setting up workflows for collaborative data collection and analysis.
- Working with data management tools available at TU Delft.
- Finding suitable solutions for data storage, efficient data retrieval, back-ups and continuous data collection.
- Using open digital platforms for showcasing research results.

SOFTWARE TESTING & AUTOMATION

- Adopting software testing best practices and implementation of automatic testing for continuous integration.
- Developing workflows to automate certain aspects of a research project, such as reading, processing and analysing data.

DOCUMENTATION

- Adopting best practices for documenting code, setting up collaborative and automatic documentation infrastructure.
- Generating metadata based on discipline-specific standards.

FAIR SOFTWARE

- Development of FAIR software and applications.
- Making existing research software compliant with FAIR principles.
- Enhance existing software through restructuring, modularisation, best practices for quality control, extensibility and maintainability.
- Source code and repository review for compliance with FAIR guidelines.
- Packaging, distribution and release of software for reproducible research.

COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENTS & VERSION CONTROL

- Setting up collaborative software development projects with version control.